

INTERRELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE REACTIVITY OF THE AUTONOMIC NERVE SYSTEM, HYPOTHALAMIC-HYPOPHYRIC NEUROSECRETORIAL SYSTEM, PROOXIDANT AND ANTIOXIDANT SYSTEM OF THE RATS' BODY.

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Conclusion. *The results of the effect of the organophosphorus pesticide chlorpyrifos on the hypothalamic-pituitary neurosecretory system of rat offspring, in case of poisoning during pregnancy and lactation, are presented. In all series of experiments, dose-dependent changes in the HPA axis of the offspring were observed, characterized by inhibition or some activation of the development and functioning of this system.*

Keywords: *Autonomic nervous system reactivity, hypothalamic-pituitary neurosecretory system, prooxidants, antioxidants, oxidative stress, homeostasis, physiological regulation, experimental studies, metabolism, rats, stress factors, biochemical markers, free radical-antioxidant balance.*

Introduction. We know that the reactivity and resistance of an individual against the influence of external factors are provided against the background of the activity of the central nervous system, the autonomic nervous system, the neuroendocrine system of the body. Any stress factors primarily act regardless of the strength, nature and duration at the level of the central system, through the receptor structures of the body. In this case, the body's response to such an irritant is provided at the level of the central nervous system, the autonomic nervous system, as well as the hypothalamic-pituitary-neurosecretory system of the body. If you pay attention to the large-cell structure of the SON and PVN is an evolutionarily old organization that through the neurohypophysis provides regulation of the peripheral endocrine glands, as well as systems and organs in the body. Since in the PVN in small-cell nuclei according to A.L. Polenov, tropic hormones such as FSH, LH, TSH, ACTH are produced. In addition, vasopressin and oxytocin are produced in large-cell nuclei. Their legendary V1, V2, V3 receptors are determined throughout the body and provide a response at these levels depending on the nature of stress factors. Provides centralization of blood circulation, constancy of water-salt metabolism. In addition, these hormones act specific character V1A and V1R blood vessels, liver, V1B, V3 adenohypophysis CNS, where it performs neurotransmitter functions. V2 located in the nephrons participates in the reabsorption of water and sodium in the blood. [8]. V1 receptor located in muscles, CNS, adrenal glands, adipose tissue, osteoclasts, osteoblasts, V1B receptor located in the adenohypophysis, in the medulla adrenal glands, pancreas alveoli provides specific response reactions [5,6]: ensures the transition of amino acids, fatty acids, glucose in the cell; ensures the combustion of these substances in the Krebs and Warburg cycle; provides through the activation of anabolic hormones in the body productive states. [7,4].

Oxytocin regulates the activity of endocrine glands, the central nervous system, and participates in the adaptation process [10]. In addition, oxytocin provides the effect of estradiol, serotonin, opioid substances, ensuring the development of pleasure from receiving adaptation. [9]. Participates in the process of autoregulation in ensuring labor, as well as the release of milk and the arousal of sexual activity, participates in the regulation of hormones of the adenohypophysis, In addition, oxytocin as a mediator ensures the development of memory, erases harmful memories, provides positive psychological states and pleasure of the body . Provides anabolic processes of sexual desire [2,3].

Thus, the hypothalamic- pituitary- neurosecretory system is a complex morphofunctional structure of the body, the study of their activity in the relationship between the autonomic nervous system, pro- and antioxidant systems of the body is a pressing problem of modern medicine.

The aim and objectives of the study. To identify the relationships between the reactivity of the autonomic nervous system and the hypothalamic-pituitary-neurosecretory system, as well as endogenous intoxication indices in mature intact male rats.

Object of the study. In connection with the stated objective, the study was conducted on 20 mongrel male rats weighing 180-220 g.

Research methods. The reactivity of the autonomic nervous system was studied using the Hildebrant coefficient.

Reactivity in the hypothalamic - pituitary -neurosecretory system (PNS , PVN) was studied using histochemical, cytophotometric, and morphometric examination methods. The functional activity of the NSC (high, moderate, and low activity) was determined by the criteria of the content of the NSC, the volume of nuclei, nucleoli, the state of the nucleolus, and chromatin in the nucleus , which includes calculating the percentage of individual types of NSC using the method of A.L. Polenov (1993) The state of the prooxidant system, the content of MDA, was determined by the method of Stalnaya I.D., Garishvili E.G. (1977). The state of the antioxidant system was studied by determining catalase (Korolyuk M.A., Ivanova L.I., Mayorova I.T., (1988) , Endogenous intoxication indices were determined using the Gabrielyan method (1991) . Statistical processing was performed using the standard Microsoft software package Office – Excel 2000.

The results obtained and their discussion

When studying the reactivity of the autonomic nervous system in intact male rats using the Hildebrant coefficient, the heart rate was 578.0 ± 13.5 times per minute, and the respiratory rate was 106.0 ± 2.5 times per minute. The Hildebrant coefficient was 5.4 ± 0.4 . If the results obtained are interpreted with the data of Vein A.M. 1991 , then That autonomic The nervous system of intact animals is in a state of mixed reactivity, balanced reactivity.

In this case, the morphofunctional reactivity of the HPA axis, i.e. the supraoptic nucleus (SON). The NSC of this nucleus in intact rats are densely located, round, oval, less often angular in shape, and are at different stages of the secretory cycle. Among the cellular formation of the nucleus, dark-staining NSC of type II predominate (Fig. 1), in which dust-like granules of PAF-positive material are detected in the form of insignificant accumulations in the perinuclear space and in places where axons pass. The cytoplasm of these cells is mostly located in the form of a rim around the nucleus and is somewhat basophilic . The nuclei of neurons are often ellipsoid in shape with a small content of chromatin, which is located in the form of separate lumps of varying size. In some nuclei, chromatin is diffusely located, the nucleolus is located mainly in the center of the nucleus. The processes of neurons are indistinct, of varying length and thickness.

Fig. 1. Neurosecretory cells of the SON in an intact rat. Stained with chrome-alum hematoxylin and counterstained with eosin. Magnification: approx. 15x, ob. 40x. The numbers indicate: 1. Neurosecretory cells of type I ; 2. Neurosecretory cells of type II ; 3. Neurosecretory cells of type III . 4. Nucleus of glial cells satellites.

In the preparations, a small amount of lightly stained type I NSC with a very loose arrangement of PAF-positive material in the cytoplasm and type III NSC with a high content of neurosecretory substances, which is detected throughout the cytoplasm of the cells, are determined. The nuclei and nucleoli in them are small in size. In addition to the specified types of NSC, a small amount of pycnomorphically altered hyperchromic type IV NSC are also determined in histological sections. The nuclei of the satellite cells are chromatic and have an oval shape. The vessels in the area of the SOJ are well defined, most of them are in a semi-collapsed state, moderately filled with formed elements of the blood.

Paraventricular nucleus (PVN). In intact rats it is a triangular formation with its base facing upward. In the dorsal part of the nucleus, the larger cells are located, while the smaller cells are located in the tapering ventral part of the nucleus. The large-cell part of the PVN is separated from the surrounding cell groups by a light acellular zone. The NSC of this nucleus vary in shape: in most cases they are round-oval, and spindle-shaped cells are less common (Fig. 2). In the PVN, in darkly staining type II NSC, as well as in the SOA, dust-like granules of PAF-positive material are found in the form of insignificant clusters mainly in the perinuclear space and at the sites of axonal origin. Between type II NSC, type I NSC are found, which are characterized by an almost complete absence of PAF-positive material.

Fig. 2. Neurosecretory cells of the PVN in an intact rat. Stained with chrome-alum hematoxylin and counterstained with eosin. Magnification: approx. 15x, ob. 40x. The numbers indicate: 1. Neurosecretory cells of type I ; 2. Neurosecretory cells of type II ; 3. Neurosecretory cells of type III ; 3. Nucleus of glial satellite cells.

Along with this, there are type III NSCs overloaded with neurosecretory material , in which neurosecretory granules occupy the entire cytoplasm, and there are many of them in the axons. Destructively altered type IV cells are detected along the periphery of the nucleus . The nuclei of the PVN NSCs are clearly visible, of varying size and shape, but most often they have an oval shape with a diffuse arrangement of chromatin, the latter is mostly located in the center of the nucleus. Consequently, type II neurosecretory cells , which are in a state of moderate functional activity, were predominant in the PVN. In the glial satellite cells, the nuclei are chromatic . The vascular network in the PVN region is well expressed, the vessels are filled with formed elements of the blood.

The GGT is weakly expressed, in the inner and outer zones of the SV the course of nerve fibers, unevenly stained with PAF, is clearly visible (Fig. 3). The GZCHNG contains a large number of neurosecretory substances both in the neurosecretory fibers and in their terminals (in the bodies of Hering), it is located diffusely and densely (Fig. 4).

Consequently, based on the presented data, it can be concluded that in the SOJ and PVN in intact rats, dark-staining type II NSCs in the stage of moderate functional activity were predominant in the secretory formula. The nuclei of glial satellite cells, which are credited with a trophic function for nerve cells, are quite clearly visible. In the SV and GGT, the GPGs are weakly detected, which may indicate the release of NSCs into the bloodstream . At the same time, in the GZCHNG, the NSCs are located more or less uniformly and the PAF is stained intensively. The vascular network in the area of the SOJ and PVN, SV, GZCHNG is without significant changes. If we interpret these data with the data of Polenov A.L. (1993), all this indicates a relatively "calm" functioning of the HPA axis and its constituent structures in intact rats.

Fig. 3. SV in an intact rat. Nerve fibers unevenly stained with NVS are visible. Staining with chrome alum hematoxylin and counterstaining eosin . Magnification approx . 20x, oblique. 100x. The numbers indicate: 1. Thin neurosecretory fibers in the hypothalamic-pituitary tract; 2. Vessels in the outer layer of the SV.

Fig. 3. Neurohypophysis in an intact rat. Diffusely and densely located NSVs are visible in the neurohypophysis. Staining with Paraldigide fuchsin according to Gomori . Magnification approx . 20x, ob. 100x.

Thus , against the background of mixed reactivity of the autonomic nervous system, a balanced state of the prooxidant and antioxidant systems of the animal organism, the SOYA and PVY of the hypothalamus are in a moderate functional state with reserve capacity for displaying the adaptive capabilities of the organism.

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